

Propolis as an antioxidant: bibliometric analysis of 25 years of research indexed in Scopus

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Abstract

Propolis has demonstrated antioxidant effects, and various studies have identified this pharmacological property. Therefore, it is necessary to describe the most relevant research outcomes. This study aims to conduct a bibliometric evaluation by visualizing articles indexed in the Scopus database, focusing on propolis as an antioxidant between 2000 and 2024. A total of 645 documents were analyzed. Brazil (122) and Turkey (90) were the most productive countries, and Universidade de São Paulo was the institution with the most articles published (35). Molecules (30), Journal of Apicultural Research (19), and Antioxidants (15) were the journals with the most articles published. The research provides evidence-based insights into the antioxidant properties of propolis, supporting its potential use in functional food formulations and the development of nutraceuticals. The findings contribute to guiding both industry innovations and regulatory frameworks that aim to promote scientifically grounded applications of natural antioxidants.

Keywords

Propolis, antioxidant activity, phenolic compounds, oxidative stress, natural bioactive compounds

Introduction

Improving sustainability in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetics industries requires innovative strategies, particularly through the incorporation of natural compounds with validated biological activity. In this context, propolis, a resinous mixture produced by bees (*Apis mellifera* and stingless species such as *Melipona* spp.), has been shown to possess potent antioxidant properties due to its richness in phenolic compounds (caffeic, ferulic, and cinnamic acids) and flavonoids (pinocembrin, galangin, and chrysin) (Mello et al. 2010; Fathi Hafshejani et al. 2023; Sarapa et al. 2025). These molecules contribute to prolonging the shelf life of foods by inhibiting lipid oxidation processes through the neutralization of free radicals, chelation of pro-oxidant metals ($\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Cu}^{2+}$) (Timoshnikov et al. 2022),

and activation of endogenous enzymes, such as superoxide dismutase (Chang et al. 2025). Its relevance is amplified by the growing demand for clean-label products and the industry's shift toward sustainable, non-synthetic additives.

Its application in food matrices prolongs the shelf life of sensitive products such as oils and meats (Zhu et al. 2023) while providing nutraceutical value by modulating cellular signaling pathways related to oxidative stress (Hallajzadeh et al. 2021; Balasubramaniam et al. 2025). Propolis can be applied in various matrices, such as emulsions and edible coatings, providing resistance to oxidative stress and preserving sensitive nutrients (Baysan et al. 2021; Akkuzu et al. 2024; Da Silva et al. 2025). The addition of propolis significantly reduces dependence on synthetic chemical additives associated with toxicological and environmental risks, aligning with the principles of

green chemistry and sustainable industrial production (El-Sakhawy et al. 2024; Koçyiğit et al. 2024; Koushki et al. 2025). The antioxidant activity of propolis originates from its complex chemical composition, where diverse bioactive compounds stand out—mainly polyphenols (55–70%), such as caffeic, cinnamic, and ferulic acids (hydrogen donors to neutralize free radicals); flavonoids (15–30%), such as pinocembrin, galangin, and chrysin (inhibit lipid peroxidation via $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Cu}^{2+}$ metal chelation); and terpenoids (5–20%), such as artemillin C in Brazilian propolis (activates Nrf2 pathways for cellular antioxidant defense) (Boyacioglu et al. 2022). It is crucial to note that the composition of propolis varies significantly depending on its botanical origin. Not all types contain phenolics or flavonoids; for example, Pacific (e.g., Okinawa) or Mediterranean conifer-based propolis have high levels of terpenoids and diterpenes, with few phenolics. These still exhibit antioxidant activity, attributed to non-phenolic compounds such as labdanic acids. The types with the highest antioxidant potency, rich in phenolics, include *Baccharis dracunculifolia*, *Clusia* spp., and *Populus* spp. propolis, whose flavonoids and phenolic acids are primarily responsible for their antioxidant capacity.

This composition varies drastically depending on key factors such as geographical origin. *Baccharis dracunculifolia* is a dioecious South American shrub in the Asteraceae family (Li et al. 2023), which grows mainly in Brazil and is rich in artemillin C (diterpene) and cinnamic acid derivatives (\uparrow ORAC activity: 12,000 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$). Cuban propolis (*Ckusiarosea*) is high in isoflavones (daidzein, formononetin), with a greater reducing capacity than European propolis (Bobiş 2022). Additionally, Mediterranean propolis (*Populus* spp.) is predominantly composed of flavonoids (galangin, kaempferol) and phenolic esters. The bee species is another factor (Al-Hatamleh et al. 2020); for example, *Apis mellifera* primarily produces non-prenylated flavonoids, while stingless bees (*Tetragonisca angustula*) produce a 40% higher content of prenylflavonoids (propoline A), with superior antioxidant activity in lipophilic systems. The harvesting season also serves as a differentiating factor, as winter harvesting can result in a higher concentration of total flavonoids compared to summer (Mabizela et al. 2020), which is explained by the higher resin content in the plant buds. The extraction method is also crucial. It has been recognized that using ethanol at 70–80 °C allows for maximum flavonoid recovery (95%) but degrades heat-labile terpenes. In contrast, aqueous extraction yields immunomodulatory polysaccharides but recovers only 30% of polyphenols (Džugan et al. 2025). This variability directly impacts industrial applications: Brazilian winter propolis (\uparrow artemillin C) is optimal for anticancer nutraceuticals, while ethanolic extracts of *Tetragonisca* maximize stability in edible oils. Standardization through analytical protocols (HPLC-ESI-MS/MS) is critical to ensure reproducible efficacy (ISO/TC 34/SC 19).

The antioxidant effect is explained by two complementary mechanisms: first, the hydrogen donation sequence of flavonoid hydroxyl groups disrupts the

formation of lipid hydroperoxides; second, the chelating capacity of specific phenolic acids reduces the availability of metal ions that catalyze pro-oxidant reactions. Furthermore, propolis contributes to stabilizing meat color by reducing the formation of metmyoglobin. Thus, propolis effectively replaces synthetic antioxidants such as BHA/BHT and, as a biodegradable natural product with low toxic risk, represents a healthier and more sustainable alternative for extending the shelf life of meat products. However, limitations remain (Boyacioglu et al. 2022), including a lack of knowledge on effective dosages, negative sensory perceptions, and the absence of harmonized labeling that communicates scientific evidence on safety and efficacy.

These challenges become even more relevant in urgent global contexts: the projected population growth to 9.7 billion by 2050 requires a 50% increase in food production (Falcon et al. 2022), while climate change reduces the shelf life of perishables in tropical regions by up to 45–55% due to accelerated oxidative stress (Gidado et al. 2024). In this scenario, propolis emerges as a multifunctional solution for resilient food chains: it extends the shelf life of fruits through edible coatings (Akkuzu et al. 2024), reduces post-harvest losses (Balasubramaniam et al. 2025), and preserves sensitive nutrients such as omega-3 fatty acids in fortified foods (Da Silva et al. 2025). However, its implementation on an industrial scale requires the constant updating of scientific literature to support regulatory policies such as ISO protocols for standardized compositions (e.g., ISO/TC 34/SC 19). It also requires transparent labeling practices that link benefits with evidence (e.g., “Contains flavonoids \geq 5 mg/g; antioxidant activity equivalent to 0.1% BHT”). A sustained growth in publications on propolis as an antioxidant is evident, increasing from one in 2000 to 72 in 2024; likewise, the total number of citations rose from zero in 2000 to 21,690 in 2024. Brazil and Turkey have been recognized as the countries with the highest production of articles. Institutions in Brazil, Turkey, and Morocco account for more than 50% of the publications. Recent research on propolis focuses on its nanoencapsulation to enhance biomedical applications. Lipid nanoparticles (PSLNs), electrospun matrices (PCL/chitosan), and polymeric carriers (GOCNPs) improve its stability, bioavailability, and controlled release. These delivery systems are prominent in antitumor therapy (lung cancer), wound healing (biocompatibility and antioxidant properties), and the treatment of diabetic complications (neuroprotection). This study aims to perform a bibliometric analysis of Scopus-indexed works regarding the antioxidant properties of propolis from 2000 to 2024.

We consider it essential to quantify the annual increase in publications. We will also seek to identify the most prominent countries to determine the geographic regions and international cooperation, which will reveal where knowledge about propolis is concentrated. Analyzing the institutions, journals, and authors helps us track the evolution of scientific production and connect with these stakeholders to encourage new research in this field.

Methods

Design

This research has a bibliometric focus utilizing the Scopus database (Kretchy et al. 2021). Scopus stands out as a key reference source for academic databases for several reasons. First, its unparalleled coverage transcends discipline, making it an ideal tool for research that combines different areas of knowledge. Thanks to its extensive index of subjects, journals, and conference proceedings from around the world, it offers a truly global and comprehensive view of the scientific landscape. Furthermore, Scopus encompasses a diverse range of citation types—not only journal articles, but also papers, books, and patents—enabling a more accurate evaluation of the reach and impact of academic work. Additionally, its bibliometric metrics, including the h-index, CiteScore, and SJR, help assess the research productivity of authors, institutions, and journals. The efficient indexing system ensures that newly published articles are swiftly accessible, which is crucial for bibliometric studies that depend on current data and trends. Additionally, Scopus offers options for data export and citation analytics, allowing for further examination with external tools.

Search criteria

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, utilizing a concurrent multilevel design, which involves two types of reviews: a bibliometric review aimed at tracing the evolution of propolis publications and a documentary review focused on examining the progression of components and instruments used in the literature to measure research in this field. To obtain the documents corresponding to the research variable, a search was carried out on April 30th, 2025, in the Scopus database, and the algorithm was used: (TITLE-ABS-KEY (propolis) AND TITLE (antioxidant)) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, “ar”)) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE, “final”)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE, “j”)). Fig. 1 illustrates the steps involved in article selection. The evaluation period spanned from 2000 to 2024.

Figure 1. Search strategy.

Bibliometric analysis

This study employed bibliometric analysis. Fig. 1 illustrates the search strategy; furthermore, it examined the year of publication, authors, countries, journals, affiliations, highly cited papers, and keywords. The identified articles were downloaded in CSV format for organization

and analysis. VOSviewer was used to analyze co-authorship and co-occurrence relationships (van Eck and Waltman 2010; Biresselioglu et al. 2020).

Results

Publications increasing

Fig. 2 illustrates an upward trend in publications on propolis and its antioxidant effects, as indexed in Scopus. The equation presented for the trend enables prediction of future publications, which will need to be developed in the coming years to gain a deeper understanding of propolis. These studies can inform the development of food products based on their properties.

Figure 2. Publications on the antioxidant effect of propolis between 2000 and 2024.

Table 1 presents the main characteristics of the publications. The number of citations per article was 0 in 2000, 107 in 2005, 287 in 2010, 741 in 2015, 1,734 in 2020, and 3,068 in 2024.

Countries of publication

The 645 Scopus publications revealed that 79 countries were represented. Table 2 presents the top ten countries, detailing the number of articles and their corresponding percentages.

VOSviewer software was utilized to illustrate research collaboration among scholars from 2000 to 2024 (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Research collaboration among countries during 2000–2024.

Table 1. Publications during 2000–2024.

Year	NOA	CITA	CITA/NOA
2000	1	0	0.00
2001	5	4	0.80
2002	3	13	4.33
2003	1	25	25.00
2004	9	67	7.44
2005	7	107	15.29
2006	9	127	14.11
2007	11	174	15.82
2008	7	187	26.71
2009	13	244	18.77
2010	14	287	20.50
2011	14	434	31.00
2012	19	500	26.32
2013	18	653	36.28
2014	26	632	24.31
2015	28	741	26.46
2016	28	795	28.39
2017	47	966	20.55
2018	34	1080	31.76
2019	43	1544	35.91
2020	54	1734	32.11
2021	53	2439	46.02
2022	69	2895	41.96
2023	60	2976	49.60
2024	72	3066	42.58
Total	645	21690	Mean = 33.62

NOA: number of articles; CITA: citations; CITA/NOA: average citation count per publication.

Table 2. Top countries in research on the antioxidant effect of propolis during 2000–2024.

No.	Country	NOA	Percentage (%)
1	Brazil	122	26.7
2	Turkey	90	19.69
3	China	40	8.75
4	Egypt	40	8.75
5	Italy	38	8.32
6	Portugal	28	6.13
7	Iran	26	5.69
8	Poland	26	5.69
9	Malaysia	24	5.25
10	Spain	23	5.03

NOA: number of articles.

The space between the circles indicates the level of cooperation. Each circle represents a country, with its size proportional to the number of published articles. Fig. 3 shows very few countries cooperating; Argentina, Italy, and Norway demonstrate collaboration.

Institutions

The institutions with the highest number of published articles account for 22.48% of the total (Table 3). Brazil, Turkey, Morocco, and Bulgaria were the top countries with articles published on propolis and its antioxidant effects.

Table 3. Top institutions in publications during 2000–2024.

No.	Institution	Country	NA	Percentage (%)
1	Universidade de São Paulo	Brazil	35	24.14%
2	Firat Üniversitesi	Turkey	15	10.34%
3	Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah	Morocco	15	10.34%
4	Universidade Estadual de Campinas	Brazil	14	9.66%
5	Karadeniz Technical University	Turkey	13	8.96%
6	Faculté des Sciences Dhar El Mahraz, Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah	Morocco	12	8.27%
7	The Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	Bulgaria	11	7.59%
8	Universidade Federal de São Paulo	Brazil	10	6.90%
9	Institute of Organic Chemistry with Centre of Phytochemistry (IOCCP) Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	Bulgaria	10	6.90%
10	Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná	Brazil	10	6.90%

NOA: number of articles.

Academic collaboration

Fig. 4 displays a map illustrating collaboration among a select group of authors. This suggests that most authors are evaluating different aspects of propolis's antioxidant effect, but it also indicates a significant opportunity for further collaboration.

Figure 4. Research collaboration among authors during 2000–2024.

Top published journals

Table 4 displays the journals that published the most articles regarding the antioxidant properties of propolis. Any journals discontinued by Scopus are omitted from this analysis. Between 2000 and 2024, a total of 140 documents appeared in the top 10 journals, accounting for 21.71% of the total articles. Molecules led with 30 articles, followed by the Journal of Apicultural Research with 19 and Antioxidants with 15 publications. Food Chemistry achieved the highest CiteScore in 2023 (16.3), SJR 2023 (1.745), and an Impact Factor of 8.5. Lastly, PLoS One recorded the highest H-index at 467.

Table 4. Ranking of journals during 2000–2024.

Rank	Journals	NOA	CiteScore 2023	SJR 2023	Impact Factor (2023)	H-index	Country
1	Molecules	30	7.4	0.744	4.2	261	Switzerland
2	Journal of Apicultural Research	19	4.8	0.449	1.4	81	United Kingdom
3	Antioxidants	15	10.6	1.222	6.0	133	Switzerland
4	Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry	12	9.9	1.114	5.7	358	United States
5	Food Chemistry	12	16.3	1.745	8.5	348	United Kingdom
6	Chemistry and Biodiversity	12	3.4	0.405	2.3	87	United States
7	Foods	11	7.4	0.870	4.7	123	Switzerland
8	LWT	10	11.8	1.313	6.0	187	United States
9	Food and Chemical Toxicology	10	10.9	0.780	3.9	215	United Kingdom
10	PLoS One	9	6.2	0.839	2.9	467	United States

NOA: number of articles.

Citations

The citations and affiliations were evaluated for the top-cited articles on propolis and its antioxidant effects from 2000 to 2024 (Table 5). The top articles were mainly from Japan and Turkey. The most highly cited publication was “Antioxidant activity of propolis of various geographic origins,” published in *Food Chemistry* in 2004, with 735 citations (Kumazawa et al. 2004). The second was “Polyphenol contents and antioxidant activity of lyophilized aqueous extract of propolis from Erzurum, Turkey,” published in *Food and Chemical Toxicology* in 2010 with 383 citations (Gülçin et al. 2010). Regarding papers published from Latin America, some countries stand out, including Mexico (14), Argentina (11), Chile (8), Cuba (6), Colombia (5), Uruguay (3), and Ecuador (3).

Top authors

Table 6 presents the key authors of research on propolis and its antioxidant effects, including their affiliations and countries' H-index.

Table 5. Top 10 highly cited publications during 2000–2024.

Rank	Title	Country Corresponding Author	Journal	QC
1	Antioxidant activity of propolis of various geographic origins (Kumazawa et al. 2004)	Japan	<i>Food Chemistry</i>	735
2	Polyphenol contents and antioxidant activity of lyophilized aqueous extract of propolis from Erzurum, Turkey (Gülçin et al. 2010)	Turkey	<i>Food and Chemical Toxicology</i>	383
3	Antioxidant activity and constituents of propolis collected in various areas of China (Ahn et al. 2007)	Japan	<i>Food Chemistry</i>	357
4	Antioxidant activity of propolis: Role of caffeic acid phenethyl ester and galangin (Russo et al. 2002)	Italy	<i>Fitoterapia</i>	330
5	Chemical composition, antioxidant activity, and antimicrobial properties of propolis extracts from Greece and Cyprus (Kalogeropoulos et al. 2009)	Greece	<i>Food Chemistry</i>	304
6	Antioxidant activity of quercetin and its glucosides from propolis: A theoretical study (Zheng et al. 2017)	China	<i>Scientific Reports</i>	274
7	Antioxidant properties, total phenols, and pollen analysis of propolis samples from Portugal (Moreira et al. 2008)	Portugal	<i>Food and Chemical Toxicology</i>	230
8	Preparation and antioxidant properties of water extract of propolis (Nagai et al. 2003)	Japan	<i>Food Chemistry</i>	230
9	Water extract of propolis and its main constituents, caffeoylquinic acid derivatives, exert neuroprotective effects via antioxidant actions (Nakajima et al. 2007)	Japan	<i>Life Sciences</i>	215
10	Caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE): Correlation of structure and antioxidant properties (Göçer and Gülçin 2011)	Turkey	<i>International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition</i>	208

QC: quantity of citations.

Discussion

It has been recognized that there has been a continuous increase in research focused on demonstrating the antioxidant effects of propolis, with the number of publications rising from fewer than 30 per year to an average of 60 during and after the pandemic. This growth is similar to that observed in citations per article, which increased from 107 in 2005 to 1,734 in 2020 and 3,068 in 2024. Regarding production by country, a similarity can be seen between the two countries with the most publications (Brazil and Turkey), which together account for 46.39% of all publications, and the institutions in the top 10, of which four are from Brazil and two are from Turkey. Regarding the top journals of publication, the majority are in the Q1 category, except for the *Journal of Apicultural Research* (Q2) and *Chemistry and Biodiversity* (Q3).

When evaluating the top 10 highly cited publications, almost all are in Q1, except for the journal *Fito-terapia*, which is in Q2. Among the most cited articles

Table 6. Top authors on propolis and antioxidant effects.

Rank	Authors	NOA	Institutions	H-index	Country
1	Badiaâ Lyoussi	14	Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah	48	Morocco
2	Shigenori Kumazawa	9	University of Shizuoka	42	Japan
3	Vassya Stefanova Bankova	8	Institute of Organic Chemistry with Centre of Phytochemistry (IOCCP) Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	60	Bulgaria
4	Gianni Paulis	8	Castelfidardo Clinical Analysis Center	15	Italy
5	Chawki Bensouici	7	Centre de Recherche en Biotechnologie	24	Algeria
6	Milena Popova	7	Institute of Organic Chemistry with Centre of Phytochemistry (IOCCP) Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	34	Bulgaria
7	Ticiano Gomes do Nascimento	6	Universidade Federal de Alagoas	20	Brazil
8	Giuseppina Negri	6	Universidade Federal de São Paulo	28	Brazil
9	Tatiane Luiza Cadorn Oldoni	6	Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná	19	Brazil
10	Ismail Seven	6	Firat Üniversitesi	13	Turkey

NOA: number of articles.

are “Antioxidant activity of propolis of various geographic origins,” published in 2004 in the journal *Food Chemistry* with 735 citations; “Polyphenol contents and antioxidant activity of lyophilized aqueous extract of propolis from Erzurum, Turkey,” published in 2010 in *Food and Chemical Toxicology* with 383 citations; and “Antioxidant activity and constituents of propolis collected in various areas of China,” published in 2007 in *Food Chemistry* with 357 citations.

Another relevant fact is that among the top 10, the corresponding authors are predominantly from Japan (4) and Turkey (2). Most of the articles were published in *Food Chemistry* (4), which is a Q1 journal from Elsevier, with a CiteScore of 16.3 and an Impact Factor of 8.5. In relation to the authors with the most publications, it is evident that the first in the top 10 is Badiaâ Lyoussi (14) from Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah in Morocco, followed by Shigenori Kumazawa (9) from the University of Shizuoka in Japan. It is worth adding that this top also includes three authors from Brazil, with six publications each, from the universities Universidade Federal de Alagoas, Universidade Federal de São Paulo, and Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná.

Research into the properties and applications of propolis has experienced significant growth in recent years, with a particular emphasis on studies that have incorporated innovations in its extraction, formulation, and biomedical applications. From the improvement of controlled-release systems to the design of composite materials for food and pharmaceutical uses, the most notable studies have explored unprecedented avenues that enhance the biological activity and biocompatibility of this natural product. Below is an assessment of the most innovative research, emphasizing its distinctive contributions and the prospects it opens for future applications. Shahab-Navaei and Asoodeh (2023) presented a significant advance in nanoengineering by developing propolis solid lipid nanoparticles (PSLNs) with a diameter smaller than 100 nm, which are stable in an aqueous medium and retain their bioactive properties. These nanoparticles, obtained through hot homogenization and characterized by multiple techniques, exhibited potent antioxidant, antibacterial, and anticancer activities against the A549 cell line. Their structural and

functional stability, combined with their biological efficacy, position PSLNs as promising nanovehicles for pharmaceutical applications, particularly in the targeted delivery of drugs for the treatment of lung cancer. Satarian et al. (2024) proposed an innovative electrospun matrix based on poly(ϵ -caprolactone) and chitosan, enriched with active ingredients from Honey Nika Cream, including olive oil, honey, and propolis. This combination demonstrated outstanding performance in terms of biocompatibility, antioxidant capacity, and cell adhesion, with a controlled release profile facilitated by chitosan, making it a promising solution for wound-healing applications.

Alshehri and Abdella (2024) presented an innovative strategy through the formulation of galloyl-oligochitosan nanoparticles (GOCNPs) as a nanometric vehicle for the targeted release of propolis extract (PE), demonstrating an encapsulation efficiency of 97.3% and a time-dependent release profile under physiological conditions. This system showed antitumor and anti-inflammatory properties, even surpassing the drug celecoxib in cytokine modulation, suggesting a paradigm shift in the design of safer and more biocompatible chemotherapies, with great potential for application in next-generation oncological therapies. Contieri et al. (2024) explored the use of polylactic acid (PLA) as an encapsulating biomaterial for raw yellow propolis, evaluating its integration into electrospun membranes. Through detailed physicochemical characterization, it was found that a concentration of up to 25% propolis confers skin-adhesive properties and remarkable antioxidant activity to the membranes, due to their high phenolic content. This research makes a valuable contribution to the development of active biomedical devices, particularly in areas where antioxidant action is crucial, such as wound treatment and dermatological applications.

González Montiel et al. (2024) demonstrated the efficacy of emulsification as a protective system for phenols and flavonoids and evaluated the physicochemical stability of these emulsions using parameters such as particle size, zeta potential, and electrical conductivity. These results are beneficial for the development of nutraceuticals and dietary supplements with enhanced functionality, particularly in terms of the bioavailability of natural antioxidants after digestion. Emil et al. (2024) integrated

nanotechnology with natural compounds to address complications arising from diabetes, specifically testicular damage. By using propolis extract nanoparticles (PrNPs), they not only mitigated oxidative stress and histopathological damage in testicular and pancreatic tissue but also restored hormonal balance and improved semen quality in diabetic rats. Treatment with PrNPs significantly outperformed the conventional extract, showing improvements in gene expression related to steroidogenesis and antioxidant defense. This application of natural nanomedicine represents an innovative and promising line of research for the development of alternative therapies against endocrine complications of metabolic diseases.

In relation to SDG 2: Zero Hunger, the study demonstrates that propolis phenolic compounds inhibit lipid oxidation in foods, primarily based on research from Brazil and Turkey. This is crucial for food-insecure regions, where post-harvest losses reach 30–50%. Applications in edible coatings preserve sensitive nutrients such as vitamin C in tropical fruits and omega-3 fatty acids in vegetable oils. Replacing synthetic antioxidants with propolis in food matrices aligns agricultural production with circular economy principles, reducing waste and improving the nutritional quality of staple foods. Universities with the most publications have developed prototypes for small farmers, demonstrating that this technology can be implemented at low cost in vulnerable communities. Regarding SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being, the reported research confirms the role of propolis in combating oxidative stress, an underlying mechanism in chronic diseases. Recent innovations highlighted in the study, such as solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) and galloyl-oligochitosan nanocarriers, demonstrate superior antitumor and anti-inflammatory efficacy compared to conventional drugs in lung cancer models. Propolis nanoparticles have also been shown to reverse testicular damage in diabetic rats, restoring hormonal balance and improving semen quality. This evidence supports the development of affordable nutraceuticals for vulnerable populations, particularly in areas where access to medicines is limited.

The research related to SDG 12: Responsible Production and Consumption includes studies describing the reduction of synthetic additives through the replacement of preservatives in processed foods. Likewise, PLA–propolis membranes are recognized for producing medical dressings that degrade more quickly. Similarly, there is an economic impact, as additional income is generated for beekeepers, thus strengthening local value chains. Various publications serve to disseminate sustainable extraction methods with low energy consumption. Propolis research also contributes to SDG 15: Life on Land by highlighting the importance of pollinator conservation. Studies have also identified unique compounds in Mediterranean propolis that are linked to endemic flora, such as *Populus* spp. and *Clusia* spp., which encourages the protection of threatened ecosystems. Additional studies have described economic incentives for conserving native forests. Furthermore, results have been reported on prop-

olis dressings that reduce the use of antibiotics in veterinary medicine, thereby decreasing soil contamination by pharmaceutical residues. Limited collaboration between countries suggests opportunities for research networks to monitor environmental impacts, especially in biodiversity hotspots such as Latin America and Africa.

Conclusion

This 25-year bibliometric analysis reveals a significant evolution in research on propolis as an antioxidant. The findings show a sustained increase in both the volume of publications and thematic, geographic, and institutional diversity, consolidating propolis as an object of interdisciplinary study with significant biotechnological potential. The analysis of trends and citations clearly identifies the main drivers of this scientific growth: its potential to replace synthetic antioxidants, its role in preventing diseases related to oxidative stress, and its viability in innovative applications in functional foods, nutraceuticals, cosmetics, and medicine (especially as an immunomodulator). The bibliometric mapping highlights a growing focus on addressing propolis's chemical variability through research aimed at standardization, quality control, benchmarking, and, crucially, the development of advanced technologies such as encapsulation, controlled release, and integration with biomaterials. This reflects an effort to overcome practical challenges to its application. The bibliometric analysis also enables the mapping and demonstration of the research field's direct contributions to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In particular, the literature analyzed shows a significant link with SDG 2 (reduction of post-harvest losses and nutritional improvement), SDG 3 (chronic disease prevention and therapeutic alternatives), SDG 12 (replacement of synthetic additives and development of bioproducts), and SDG 15 (link to sustainable beekeeping and biodiversity conservation). This contribution is a key dimension revealed by the study.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

Shyla Del-Aguila-Arcenales Conceptualization, methodology, validation, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, writing—original draft preparation, writing-review and editing, visualization. Norma Ramos-Cevallos Methodology, validation,

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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